

Query Generators for Datasets of Interchangeable Recipe Steps

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Abstract

Actions, like "cook chicken," "change tire," and "fold paper," have start and end states. Furthermore, a single action like "cook chicken" starting with a particular start state can have multiple possible end states like baked, fried, or boiled. Some of these possible end states may be unacceptable depending on the situation: boiling breaded chicken is less tasty than frying it. Training models to understand which actions are swappable with each other—which actions can be swapped with each other and still produce a possible and acceptable end state—would also allow them to reason about the relationship between the start state and the action an entity goes through. Models that understand how to evaluate the swappability of two steps can better understand, modify, and generate procedural text, like instructions. Currently existing models struggle to reason about these events because of the highly variable and context-sensitive nature of an action's effect. To make progress toward understanding events, we focus on recipes as a subset of procedural text with an abundance of online resources. We present a seed query database containing possibly swappable steps for recipes and a generalizable to automatically generate new datasets from other instruction-based text. Our method clusters Sentence Transformers embeddings created from recipe titles so that recipes with similar end states are grouped together. Inside these clusters, we generate possible replacements from recipe steps that share a marginal amount of similarity. After clustering a set of 600 recipes by cosine similarity and analyzing differences between recipes in each individual cluster, we found splitting the set into 50 clusters to be most optimal. Applying our methodology onto these 50 clusters, we are able to generate approximately 80,000 queries. Our library is a stepping stone for the future development of models that are capable of modifying instructions without changing final results.

Keywords: Natural Language Processing, Event Reasoning, Procedural Text, Dataset Generation.

1. Introduction

An event consists of an action that modifies some state, while procedural text aims to describe a sequence of events to be executed in series. In our investigation, we consider pairs of swappable events, where replacing one of the two events with the other results in an equivalent (or close to equivalent) end state.

However, within the vast space of recipe steps of all recipes, very few pairs of steps will be swappable with each other because they are either parts of completely separate recipes or they mention objects that are foreign to the other step’s recipe. For example, one recipe step may mention using a stand mixer that is assumed to be present, while a second recipe step (from a different recipe) may recommend using a hand whisk. If we replace the second recipe step with the first recipe step in the second step’s recipe, their contextual incompatibilities will make them not swappable, even if other elements were so. The goal of this paper is to, through a combination of searching and automated generation; create replacements for specific recipe steps. We call a pair consisting of a specific recipe step and its possible replacement a query. For each recipe, we generate replacements for its steps by limiting the number of recipes and steps that our algorithm searches for to those that are sufficiently relevant to the original recipe. We also preserve the original grammatical structure of the recipe step to be replaced by surgically replacing specific parts of speech. Our method greatly increases the number of swappable queries, ensuring that if two steps are indeed swappable, we are not impeded from detecting them due to external barriers.

We make the following contributions to generating queries:

- A library for generating structure-preserving queries through incremental modification
- A seed database generated from the library.

2. Related Work

State tracking has long been explored as an avenue for helping models gain a semantic understanding of language of various forms and expressions. By generating structured information, models can make better inferences and predictions about the medium that they are interacting with. Since state tracking often contains long-range dependencies, recurrent neural networks were explored as a plausible architecture. [1] applies them to track the state of dialogue, with high accuracy on the DSTC2 dataset [2]. Similarly, [5] used them to extract specific events that occurred in a text. With the advent of parallelizable transformer model architectures following [8], [1] used an attention-based method and newer word embeddings to achieve higher accuracy in dialog state tracking. Recent research has also tried to help models not only parse and categorize events from language, but understand the relationships and dependencies that events have with one another. [9] created a dataset based on Wikihow that contains connections between

various steps, including dependence and temporal relations, which are present in the successful completion of a goal. [10] further extends this research by creating a wikiHow knowledge base created through linking similar steps from different articles. Our research aims to not only link steps between recipes but to use them to generate new possible replacements that still make grammatical and contextual sense.

3. Methods

Our method allows for the rapid generation of queries for a recipe step by incrementally modifying it based on other steps from other recipes. These other recipes are the most similar to the original recipe and so their states generally lead to similar end states. See the flowchart below that describes the general structure of our methodology:

Figure 1. Flowchart

3.1 SentenceTransformers

The SentenceTransformers framework, created by [7], uses pre-trained state-of-the-art BERT transformer models in order to convert phrases or instructions into a vector embedding encoding the meaning of its input. We extensively use these encodings in order to calculate the cosine similarity between any two phrases, which represents how close they are semantically. As a result, we decide to use the multi-qa-MiniLM-L6-cos-v1 model, because it is generalizable and creates normalized embeddings, allowing us to optimize cosine similarity computations into dot products [7] model.

3.2 Clustering

Our library first assumes that the dataset will have recipes with both a title and a list of recipe steps. Our library uses the SentenceTransformers framework from [7] in order to first turn all recipe titles into vector embeddings. It then uses Agglomerative Clustering, implemented by [6], in order to recursively cluster title embeddings using cosine similarity as the linkage distance.

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This method ensures that recipes with similar titles (which is a good metric for the result, or end-state, of a recipe) are compared, giving us the greatest chance of finding two recipes with roughly similar steps.

3.3 Parsing

Once clustering has finished, the algorithm begins to parse each recipe to extract its steps. Since most recipe steps are imperative commands with a specified direct object and possibly some prepositions, these were our primary focus of parsing. First, all sentences in a recipe step are split from each other. Using the spaCy library's `en_core_web_trf_model` (which prioritizes accuracy), these sentences are then parsed out into a tree of tokens. Second, these sentences are split into independent clauses, detected by coordinating conjunctions over verbs. Finally, each independent clause is traversed (via the spaCy-generated tree) to find the main verb, direct objects, and prepositional clauses (which may indicate position, time, etc.), which are important for maintaining the context of newly created instructions. If the verb is empty or a stop word, or all direct objects are stop words, the clause is considered unparseable and ignored.

3.4 Query Generation

Queries are generated pairwise between parseable steps from different recipes.

If the cosine similarity of step 1 and step 2, from different recipes, is between 0.40 and 0.83 (where steps are semantically close enough but not identical), we make a new query that seeks to replace step 1 by replacing the verb of the original step with the verb of the other step, with all other elements being preserved.

If the cosine similarity between any of the direct objects of step 1 and any of the direct objects of step 2 is between 0.40 and 0.83, we create a new query for step 1 by replacing as many of the direct objects of step 1 with direct objects of the other step, with all other elements being preserved.

If both conditions above apply, we make a new query for step 1 by applying both procedures as described above.

Generating Direct Objects: Our approach helps generate new sets of direct objects with incremental differences. Let us consider two sets of direct objects, A and B, where we are trying to replace elements of A with elements of B. Each element of A selects two candidates from B with the greatest semantic similarity with itself such that this similarity lies between 0.4 and 0.83. Each of these candidates from B accepts the choice from A with the highest similarity. Each element of A is then replaced with an element of B that accepted it with the highest similarity, given that such an element exists.

4. Results and Discussion

Our algorithm was able to generate approximately 80,000 queries from a subset of 600

recipes from a recipe dataset provided by [4]. In order to expand the number of queryable recipes, we can randomly remove pairs of recipes or their steps from inspection.

4.1 Clustering Recipes

Results from clustering our sample of 600 recipes, shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3, indicate that both the mean and minimum pairwise similarities (maximum linkage distance) of the clusters increase roughly linearly with the number of clusters that we set. We also find that with more clusters, variance in the number of recipes per cluster as well as the size of outlier clusters with disproportionately many recipes decrease. Due to these reasons and computational constraints, we chose to run our experiment by splitting the recipe set into 50 clusters.

Figure 2. Cluster sizes and cosine similarities between different titles.

Figure 3. Maximum and mean cluster sizes with standard deviation

4.2 Recipe Generation Examples

Taken from two recipes, the first being a recipe on breakfast pizza, and the other being chinese chop suey, we extract the following queries for replacing steps of the breakfast pizza:

- “cut sausage into small pieces”, ”slice sausage into small pieces”
- “cut sausage into small pieces”, ”reduce sausage into small pieces”
- “whisk eggs, and milk in a bowl until frothy”, “whisk eggs, and cup of soy sauce in a bowl until frothy”

4.3 Clause/Query Representation

Since, we had initially confirmed the structure of any parseable clause, its sentence representation is reconstructed in the following order (as in the examples above):

1. main verb
2. direct objects, separated with commas and “ands”
3. all other prepositional clauses in sequential order.

If a clause is not parseable, it is just represented in its original form. Note that these queries still retain grammatical structure, despite some of the verbs and objects being replaced, which allows it to be reasonably placed in a labeling task.

5. Conclusion and Future Work

We present a library that can algorithmically generate possible replacements for recipe steps while preserving grammar and contextual information. Our library has applications for models that are capable of analyzing and understanding imperative sequences of text. These models are able to replace steps with the knowledge that the changes that they make will not change the end result or to a miniscule degree, and even answer questions about said steps. Future extensions of our work may also apply to more irregular, non-recipe text, such as stories or news. Future progress will involve trying to generalize this parsing algorithm so that it is able to understand imperative structures that are more subtle and indirect. This is especially the case in text other than recipes, where commands may merge with other clauses.

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